

USAGE OF PHRASES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

K.Kakharov

Associate Professor of Fergana State University
qobili7000@gmail.com

D.Dehqonova

Student of Fergana State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11220581>

Abstract. This article talked about the concept of phraseologism, its development and importance. Also, the use of expressions in English and Uzbek languages, their characteristics, similarities and differences were also explained. In addition, valuable sources that have a great place in Uzbek and English linguistics and brief comments on them were also given. In addition, this article suggested the problems that arose in the process of translating phraseological units in two languages and effective solutions to them. The benefits of comparing two languages to language learners and nations were also highlighted.

Key words: phraseology, phraseologism, expression, synonymy, emotional-expressive color, linguo-cultural features, meaning, figurative meaning.

Introduction

One of the important fields of linguistics is the study of phraseology. Initially emerging as an independent branch of linguistics in the 1940s, this field encompasses the study of the synonymous, homonymous, and antonymous characteristics of idiomatic expressions. Additionally, the phraseology section examines the words within idioms, their meanings, and their relationships with other parts of speech.

The role of idiomatic expressions in both English and Uzbek, belonging to two different language families, is unparalleled. In both languages, idioms are widely used to enhance the effectiveness of speech and to add emotional-expressive nuances.

This article discusses the application and unique features of idioms in English and Uzbek, the linguistic and cultural differences between them, and the challenges encountered in translating idioms from one language to another. Furthermore, it presents effective translation methods and techniques to overcome these challenges.

Literature Review and Methods

The study of idiomatic expressions in Uzbek linguistics began in the 1950s. Since then, several linguists, including Sh. Rahmatullayev, B. Yuldoshev, and A. Mamatov, have conducted extensive research in various areas of phraseology. They have developed dictionaries that encapsulate the meanings, synonyms, homonyms, and antonyms of idiomatic expressions. Notably, Sh. Rahmatullayev's «Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language» is considered a valuable resource in Uzbek linguistics.

In English linguistics, significant contributions to the study of idioms include «Idioms: Description, Comprehension, Acquisition, and Pedagogy» by Dmitri Leontjev and Elena Babenko, and «The Oxford Dictionary of English Idioms.» These books provide clear examples of English idioms and their meanings. Additionally, they offer information on the synonymous and antonymous variants of idioms and their brief etymological backgrounds.

Another important resource in English linguistics is «In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation» by Mona Baker. This book is particularly valuable for linguists and translators. It explains the similarities and differences in linguistics between English and other languages, covering aspects from word meanings to linguistic-cultural features in a straightforward manner. The book also provides a detailed analysis of the problems encountered during the translation process from English to other languages, offering solutions and recommendations. Furthermore, it includes practical exercises to apply and reinforce the learned knowledge and experiences.

Results and Discussion

In both English and Uzbek, idioms often consist of two or more words, and the words within the idiom lose their literal meanings. The meaning of an idiom is understood through the figurative use of the words it comprises. Sometimes, the words within an idiom can retain their literal meanings. For example, in the sentence «Qizaloqning zo'rg'a tutgan kapalagi uchib ketdi» (The girl's barely caught butterfly flew away), we can analyze «kapalagi» as the subject and «uchib ketdi» as the predicate. However, in the phrase «Ertasiga ot og'rib qolsa bo'ladimi! Kapalagim uchib ketdi» (Oybek, Qutlug' qon), «kapalagim uchib ketdi» (literally «my butterfly flew away») is an idiom meaning «to be very frightened» or «to be very angry.» Here, the words lose their literal meanings and are used figuratively, so «kapalagim uchib ketdi» is considered as one predicate. Similarly, the English idiom «feather in your cap» might be literally translated as «qalpoqdagi pat» (a feather in the cap), but idiomatically it means «an achievement to be proud of.»

Idioms are created through the culture, traditions, history, and development of a language and its people. Therefore, the phraseology of each language reflects the historical, social, and cultural characteristics of that language and its people. For example, the English idiom «the green-eyed monster» means jealousy, as green is associated with envy and jealousy in English culture. This idiom originates from Shakespeare's play «Othello»: «O! beware my lord of jealousy; it is the green-eyed monster which doth mock The meat it feeds on.» Thus, understanding idioms in other languages requires knowledge of their history, religion, culture, and literature.

Some English idioms have equivalents in Uzbek. For example, «to make a mountain out of a molehill» and «to make an elephant out of a fly» correspond to the Uzbek idiom «pashshadan fil yasamoq» (to make an elephant out of a fly), meaning to exaggerate something trivial. However, some English idioms do not have exact equivalents in Uzbek, and vice versa. For instance, the Uzbek idiom «tepa sochi tikka bo'ldi» (literally «the hair on the top of the head stood up») does not have a direct equivalent in English, so its meaning can only be explained with words (to get angry).

From the above points, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Idiomatic expressions are an important part of the vocabulary in both Uzbek and English.
- In both languages, idioms are used to enhance the impact of speech and add emotional-expressive color.
- Both languages have idiomatic expressions with synonyms, antonyms, and homonyms.
- The creation and development of idioms are influenced by the historical, social, and cultural life of the people.

- Idiomatic expressions reflect the culture, worldview, and lifestyle of each nation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, idiomatic expressions play a significant role in the enrichment of a language's vocabulary. Through the use of idioms, we can gain insights into the cultural structure of society. In English, idioms are mainly based on historical events and cultural traditions. On the other hand, Uzbek idioms are closely linked to the people's lifestyle, hospitality, and rich traditions. Idioms make our speech more impactful and help us express our thoughts more effectively.

Although English and Uzbek idioms differ in their linguistic origins and cultural bases, studying these idioms in depth can serve as a bridge between speakers of these languages. By conducting comparative analyses, we can provide learners with an additional advantage, thereby strengthening intercultural and interlingual relations.

References:

1. Dilin Liu. "Idioms: Description, Comprehension, Acquisition, and Pedagogy". – Taylor & Francis, 2017.
2. <https://uz.wiktionary.org>
3. M. Baker. "In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation". London: Routledge, 1992.
4. Oxford dictionary of idioms.
5. Qosimova A. "O'zbek va ingliz frazeologiyasi". – Scientific progress, 2021. ("Uzbek and English phraseology").
6. Qahramonova D. "O'zbek va ingliz tillari idiomalarini taqqoslashning lingual tahlili". – Ustozlar uchun, 2023. ("Lingual analysis of the comparison of Uzbek and English idioms").
7. Rahmatullayev. Sh "O'zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug'ati". – O'qituvchi, 1978.
8. Urokov Sh, Isayeva M. "Linvokulturologik iboralar va ularning semantik ma'nolari". – "Sharq tillarini o'qitishning dolzarb masalalari" mavzusidagi ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya, 2022. ("Linvocultural expressions and their semantic meanings").